

Golden jubilee of the saga of aluminium isopropoxide[†]

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In spite of the well-known applications of aluminium isopropoxide in Meerwein-Ponndorf type of catalytic reactions since the early 1920's, the actual nature of this simple compound was surprisingly obscure. This brief article highlights the work during the last 50 years of the senior author by explaining the changes in its molecular complexity on ageing as well as its extensive applications as a precursor for the synthesis of a large variety of homo- and heterobimetallic isopropoxide systems by facile reactions.

The chemistry of the well-known Meerwein-Ponndorf catalyst : 'aluminium isopropoxide' was surprisingly shrouded in mystery upto 1950's. Even its molecular complexity had been reported to vary from 2-8 by well-known authorities¹⁻³ in the field. However, taking a clue from the 'ageing property' of Al(OH)₃, Mehrotra clarified the confusion by showing that Al(OPrⁱ)₃ (dimeric in vapour state) distils to a trimeric liquid at about 100° under 0.1 mm pressure, but this liquid solidifies to a crystalline tetrameric product on standing for about a week, followed by extremely slow further polymerization on long storage.

A plausible structure : [(PrⁱO)₂Al(μ-OPrⁱ)₂Al(OPrⁱ)₂] was inferred for the dimeric in vapour state and the interesting structure, Al{(μ-OPrⁱ)₂Al(OPrⁱ)₂}₃ was suggested⁶ in 1960 and confirmed by X-ray crystallographically⁷ in 1979 for the tetrameric stable variety, which has a central hexacoordinated aluminium ligated by 3 tetrahedral {Al(OPrⁱ)₄} units. Further polymerization does occur, albeit extremely slowly by the surrounding tetrahedral Al atoms also tending to become hexacoordinate.

The above 'ageing phenomenon' suggested⁴ for the first time in the case of {Al(OPrⁱ)₃}_n has later proved to be a general characteristic of metal alkoxide systems.

Utility of the concept of ageing phenomenon

As the concept of ageing phenomenon of Al(OPrⁱ)₃ appeared to be a general one, Mehrotra was advised to publish the same in some better known journal. However, the fact that worthwhile results even in the *Journal of Indian Chemical Society* attract considerable attention was evident by the comments from a number of probing enquiries from M/s Harshaw Chemical Company at Cleveland, USA, the

largest producer of Al(OPrⁱ)₃ in the world.

During a lecture tour of USA in 1961, Mehrotra had an unscheduled stopover for a few hours in Cleveland and tried to contact the R/D director of M/s Harshaw company and was surprised by the spontaneous reply on telephone, whether he was the same Mehrotra who had published about the 'ageing phenomenon' of Al(OPrⁱ)₃ in 1953. Thereafter, Prof. Mehrotra was very courteously invited to their R/D laboratory, in order to discuss their problem arising from numerous complaints especially of the small consumers about the quality of Al(OPrⁱ)₃ which was supplied by the company.

On being informed that such small consumers often tended to store their product for a long time before distillation according to their need, Mehrotra remarked that their difficulty could be ascribed to the 'ageing effect' enhancing the molecular association of their samples. If heated at too fast a rate, the 'aged' sample could not get enough heat required for its depolymerization upto the expected boiling point, but then distilled over too fastly at a higher temperature on attaining the dimeric form. Such consumers should be advised to heat their samples rather slowly at the initial stage, till some frothing was visible near the boiling point and thereafter {Al(OPrⁱ)₃}₂ would distil in a docile manner. On noticing a reaction of disbelief, he called for a sample received back by the company and demonstrated the correctness of his suggestion by heating the sample fastly when it poured over at about 150-160°/1 mm, but distilled at a requisite rate on keeping the bath for a few minutes at about 100° and raising the same by a few degrees after frothing was clearly visible.

The Director of the company was highly pleased to get

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi, discussion with whom by the senior author have been highly helpful to him.

rid of the bad reputation accruing to the company due to the complaints of the large number of small consumers and continued to assist Mehrotra by gifts of rare chemicals required by him for his research pursuit back in India.

Synthetic uses of $\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$

Like metal alkoxides in general, $\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ also is a reactive species which can be ascribed to the presence of electronegative alkoxy groups making the metal atom highly prone to nucleophilic attack.

Besides other applications, $\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ has been utilized for the synthesis of a variety of products by treating it with a number of organic compounds having a reactive hydroxy group, e.g. alcohols and β -diketones etc., yielding products like $\text{Al}(\text{OR})_3$ (R = primary or secondary alkyl groups), $\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)(\text{OR})_2$ (R = tertiary alkyl groups) and $\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_{3-n}(\beta\text{-diket})_n$ (where $n = 1, 2, 3$)⁹⁻¹¹, respectively. The above reactions have been carried out in benzene, which forms a lower boiling azeotrope with isopropyl alcohol. Using this technique, the reactions can be carried out in any desired molar ratio and the rate of replacement as well as the completion of the reaction can be checked by the estimation of isopropyl alcohol in distillate by a simple oxidimetric procedure.

As is well-known¹²⁻¹⁵, metal alkoxides tend to undergo oligomerization through alkoxy bridges, but their degree of association is lowered by steric bulk of the alkyl groups. For example, ethoxide and isopropoxide of aluminium depict tetrameric behaviour, but the tertiary butoxide is dimeric⁴ (in contrast to tertiary butoxides of titanium and zirconium, which are monomeric). This difference has been explained by the stronger bridging tendency in $[(\text{Bu}^t\text{O})_2\text{Al}(\mu\text{-OBU}^t)_2\text{Al}(\text{OBu}^t)_2]$ due to electron deficient nature of aluminium. The same effect is observed in the ready replacement of all the three isopropoxide groups forming higher primary tri-alkoxides, e.g. $[\text{Al}(\text{OBU}^n)_3]_4$, but the reaction of $[\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_3\}_4]$ with tertiary butanol yields mainly $[(\text{Bu}^t\text{O})_2\text{Al}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}(\text{OBu}^t)_2]$ as further replacement becomes extremely slow.

Synthesis of aluminium tri-carboxylates

In 1949, Gray and Alexander¹⁶ described in detail, the reasons for the failures¹⁷⁻²² of a large number of workers to prepare aluminium tri-carboxylates, coming finally to the conclusion that for a variety of stated physicochemical reasons, such tri-carboxylates could not exist at all. In addition to several other starting materials, McBain and McLatchie^{23,24} had attempted to prepare aluminium tri-

carboxylates by the reaction of aluminium secondary butoxide with fatty acids, but none of their products showed $\text{RCOO} : \text{Al}$ ratio higher than 2.

Suspecting that such results could be due to the stable bridged structure, which rendered the replacement of the third group much less facile, Mehrotra attempted the reaction of $\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ with carboxylic acids under milder conditions. He succeeded in synthesizing pure tri-stearate and tripalmitate of aluminium for the first time by the reactions of $\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ with 3 moles of carboxylic acids in benzene with the experimental observations shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Mehrotra was conscious that the conclusion would be valid in the above 1:3 reaction only if the moisture had not crept in the system, the final product isolated by removal of volatile organic solvents could be a mixture of $\text{Al}(\text{OH})(\text{OOCR})_2$ and RCOOH and differentiation by mere C, H and Al analyses could not be adequate. In spite of such lurking doubts, he published²⁵ the results as he had used the system for the synthesis of a large variety of other even more hydrolyzable alkoxide products.

In spite of his own doubts, he was surprised by the receipt of a highly condemning letter from Prof. Alexander's colleague that the conclusion was not based on incontrovertible grounds and Mehrotra was extremely pained by the overall remarks that 'this publication was also like that of other Indian chemists, who often publish such unconfirmed results'. In spite of his grief, Mehrotra replied indicating that he was conscious of the weakness of his arguments, but the same could be confirmed by carrying out the reaction of RCOOH and $\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ in a ratio greater than 3:1, followed by lixiviating the product by some suitable solvent which could separate out excess carboxylic acid. He, however, expressed his inability to carry out any further experimental work immediately, as he had performed the experiments only in the last 3-4 days of his stay in London and had thereafter, returned to India, where he had no facilities for such work involving stringent anhydrous systems.

Conclusions

The above account shows a highly interesting development in the chemistry of aluminium isopropoxide starting with its unique 'ageing property' to the synthesis of a large number of heterometallic isopropoxide systems containing $[Al(OPr^i)_4]^-$ and $[Al(OPr^i)_2]^+$ moieties.

References

- H. Ulich and W. Nespital, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1933, **165**, 294.
- R. A. Robinson and D. A. Peak, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1935, **39**, 1125.
- S. M. McElvain and W. R. Davie, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 1400.
- R. C. Mehrotra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **30**, 585.
- R. C. Mehrotra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **31**, 85 and 904.
- D. C. Bradley, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1960, **2**, 303.
- N. Ya. Turova, V. A. Kuzunov, A. I. Yanovskii, N. G. Borkii, Yu. T. Struchkov and B. L. Tarnopolskii, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1979, **41**, 5.
- J. G. Oliver and I. J. Worrall, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1969, **5**, 455.
- R. K. Mehrotra and R. C. Mehrotra, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1961, **39**, 795.
- Y. P. Singh and A. K. Rai, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1982, **12**, 85.
- J. H. Wengrovius, M. F. Garbauskas, E. A. Williams, R. C. Going, p. E. Donahue and I. F. Smith, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **108**, 982.
- D. C. Bradley, R. C. Mehrotra and W. Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 2027 and 4204.
- D. C. Bradley, R. C. Mehrotra and W. Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 5020.
- D. C. Bardley, R. C. Mehrotra and W. Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1634 and 2025.
- D. C. Bradley, R. C. Mehrotra, A. Singh and I. P. Rothwell, "Alkoxo and Aryloxo Derivatives of Metals", Academic, London, 2002.
- U. R. Gray and A. E. Alexander, *J. Phys. Chem.* 1949, **53**, 23.
- E. Markowicz, *Farben Ztg.*, 1928, **34**, 326.
- W. Ostwald and R. riedal, *Kolloid*, 1934, **69**, 185.
- G. H. Smith, H. H. Pomeroy, G. G. McGee and K. J. Mysels, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1053.
- T. S. McRoberts and J. H. Schulman, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (A)*, 1950, **200**, 136.
- W. W. Harple, S. E. Wiberley and W. H. Bauer, *Anal. Chem.*, 1952, **24**, 635.
- A.S.C. Lawerance, *J. Inst. Petroleum*, 1945, **31**, 303.
- J. W. McBain and W. L. McLatchie, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **36**, 2567.
- J. W. McBain and W. L. McLatchie, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **65**, 3266.
- R. C. Mehrotra, *Nature*, 1953, **74**, 172.
- K. C. Pande and R. C. Mehrotra, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1956, **286**, 291.
- R. C. Mehrotra and K. C. Pande, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1956, **2**, 60.
- A. Gilmour, A. Jabling and S. M. Nelson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 1972.
- M. Aggrawal, C. K. Sharma and R. C. Mehrotra, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1983, **13**, 571.
- R. C. Mehrotra and A. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **70**, 885.
- A. Mehrotra and R. C. Mehrotra, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **11**, 2170.
- R. C. Mehrotra and M. M. Agrawal, unpublished results, 1968.
- H. Albers. M. Deutsch. W. Krastinant and H. Von Asten, *Chem. Ber.*, 1952, **85**, 267.
- R. C. Mehrotra, A. K. Rai and N. C. Jain, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **40**, 349.
- J. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, **23**, 1046.
- R. K. Dubey, A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, **31**, 156.
- R. C. Mehrotra, *Coord. Chem. (IUPAC)*, 1981, **21**, 113.
- A. Shah, J. Singh, A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 1018.
- J. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1984, **13**, 273.
- R. C. Mehrotra and J. Singh *Can. J. Chem.*, 1984, **62**, 1003.
- J. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1984, **522**, 211.
- R. C. Mehrotra, S. Goel, R. B. King and K. C. Nainan, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1978, **29**, 131.
- J. A. Meese-Marktscheffel, R. Fukuchi, M. K. Kido, G. Tachibana, C. M. Jensen and J. W. Gilje, *Chem. Mater.*, 1993, **5**, 755.
- M. Bhagat, A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Main Group Met. Chem.*, 1997, **20**, 89.
- R. C. Mehrotra and A. Singh, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, under publication, 2003.
- M. Sharma, A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 1209.
- M. Sharma, A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2002, **32**, 1223.
- M. K. Sharma, A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 410.
- M. Sharma, A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Polyhedron*, 2000, **19**, 77.

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50. M. Sharma, A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Main Group Met. Chem.*, 2000, **23**, 285.
51. M. K. Sharma, A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2002, **28**, 1220.
52. R. C. Mehrotra, *Mater. Res. Soc. Symp.*, 1988, **121**, 81.
53. R. C. Mehrotra, *Chemtracts*, 1990, **2**, 389.
54. R. C. Mehrotra, *Struct. Bonding*, 1992, **77**, 1.
55. R. C. Mrhrotra, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids*, 1992, **145**, 1.
56. R. C. Mehrotra, *J. Sol-Gel Sci. Tech.*, 1994, **2**, 1.
57. R. C. Mehrotra "Heterometal alkoxides as precursors in the Sol-Gel Process", ed. Y. A. Attia, Plenum, New York, 1994, pp. 41-60.
58. R. C. Mehrotra and A. Singh, *Phosphorus, Sulfur Silicon*, 1997, **124**, 153.
59. R. C. Mehrotra and A. Singh, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1996, **26**, 1.